

Synthetic methanol for shipping decarbonisation

PROMOTIONAL TOOLKIT AND WEBSITE

Deliverable D7.2

PROJECT NO	101117616
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DURATION	48 months until 31.08.2027

Funded by
the European Union

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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public – fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

CHANGE CONTROL

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01	15.05.2024	Initial draft	Natalia Radanovic, Paul Haering	SIG
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document constitutes the deliverable D7.2 “Promotional toolkit and website” drafted in the context of Task 7.2 “Promotional toolbox and communication campaign” (M1-M48). This deliverable provides brief information on the POSEIDON website to be publicly launched by the end of Mai 2024 (M9) and the project’s communication materials.

The second chapter is dedicated to the communication materials. It gives an overview of the communication materials (e.g. flyer, roll-up) that were developed during the first nine months of the project. They will guide and support the partners in communicating about the project, in disseminating project results (e.g., at fairs and conferences, meetings with stakeholders) and in informing all target groups on the public website and social media channels.

The third chapter focuses on the project website. It describes the structure, content and the most important features of the POSEIDON website (<https://project-poseidon.eu>) conceived to be as relevant as possible to all target stakeholders (e.g. scientific community, policy makers and general public). The website was designed by the German design agency Die Komplizen (<https://komplizen.de>) under the guidance of CDE leader Steinbeis. The project website provides general information about the project, features a latest news and events section, and links to the project publications, public deliverables and social media channels (LinkedIn and X).

AUTHORS’ NOTE

The drafting of D7.2 has been inspired by similar deliverables of the projects CAPTUS (GA number 101118265) and FLEX4FACT – Industrial Cluster FLEXibility platform for sustainable FACTories to reduce CO₂ emissions and to enable the energy transition (GA number 101058657). These projects are similar in terms of types of organisations, overall objectives and impacts, as well as CDE strategy. Please note that Steinbeis 2i (S2i) is the author of the aforementioned deliverables and CDE leader within the projects CAPTUS and FLEX4FACT.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of this deliverable (D7.2) is to present the main content and features of the **POSEIDON communication materials** and **website** as well as how content management will be managed during the project lifetime. This report is strongly linked with deliverable D7.1 on CDE plan describing the overall strategy for communication, dissemination, and exploitation of the POSEIDON project.

The communication materials will guide and support the partners in communicating about the project (e.g., at fairs and conferences, meetings with stakeholders), in raising awareness of the project and its results and in providing links to the project website and social media channels. Chapter 2 is dedicated to the description of the developed POSEIDON promotional toolkit and chapter 3 will provide an overview of the project website.

The POSEIDON website is currently under construction and will be launched by start of June 2024 (M10). It was set up in responsive design in order to be correctly displayed on any type of device (ranging from regular PC to mobile devices). The website represents a key communication channel of the project and serves as main repository for public project documents and outcomes throughout the project lifetime.

The development and management of the communication materials and webpage involve several partners. The responsibilities of the different partners are as follows:

- Steinbeis works on the first version of materials and contents to be developed and asks partners for validation before publication. Steinbeis is responsible for updating communication materials and the project webpage to reflect changes,
- The design agency Die Komplizen supports Steinbeis in the development of materials and ensures that everything published meet high quality standard and is in line with POSEIDON's corporate identity,
- All POSEIDON partners provide content in the form of pictures or texts, review the final version, and give their consent for publication.

2 PROMOTIONAL TOOLKIT

In conformity with the POSEIDON project communication and dissemination strategy presented in deliverable D7.1, **project templates**, a **flyer**, a **roll-up**, a **project presentation**, a **project video**, a **project press package** and **project newsletters** will be produced to raise awareness of the project. **Social media channels** will also be used to regularly communicate about the project. All these materials form the POSEIDON promotional toolkit.

A distinction can be made between two types of material: static material, which corresponds to printed documents that, once produced, will remain largely unchanged, such as the project leaflet

and roll-up, and dynamic material, which corresponds to digital material that will be regularly updated and provide up-to-date information on the project and its progress. Most communication materials will be available on the project's sharepoint, as well as on the project website.

2.1 CORPORATE IDENTITY

The project corporate identity consists of a project logo, fonts and colors to be used for the different communication and dissemination materials to be produced. It was co-developed together with a design agency contracted by partner Steinbeis. A guidebook is available on the project sharepoint (available via [this link](#)) to help project partners best use the project logos and different fonts and colors.

2.1.1 PROJECT LOGO

The logo was chosen from 4 proposals following a vote involving all project partners. The official logo is available in different formats on the project sharepoint (available via [this link](#)).

Synthetic methanol for shipping decarbonisation

Figure 1: POSEIDON project logo with project claim

2.1.2 PROJECT FONTS

The official fonts of the project CI are called “Nazalisation” and “Public Sans“. The different types of the font to be used are as follows:

- “Nazalisation” for short headlines
- “Public sans bold” and “Public sans extra bold” for headlines and highlights,
- “Public sans regular” and “Public sans extra light” for the body text,
- “Public sans extra light italic” for captions.

Short headline	NASALIZATION Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0	
Headline	PUBLIC SANS BOLD Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0	PUBLIC SANS EXTRA BOLD Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0
Bodytext	PUBLIC SANS REGULAR Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0	PUBLIC SANS EXTRALIGHT Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0
Caption	PUBLIC SANS EXTRA LIGHT ITALIC Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0	

Figure 2: Official fonts of project POSEIDON

The official fonts can be downloaded from websites like DaFont or other trusted sources and then, once installed, they will be available in Word and other Microsoft Office applications. However, for some documents such as project deliverables, it was decided to use the “Arial” font which is more common and more adapted to long texts.

2.1.3 PROJECT COLORS

There are 3 main colors and 4 secondary colors. The primary colors derived from the project logo to be used in the main documents and publications are as follows:

- Green,
- Light blue,
- Dark blue.

The secondary colors to be used primarily for graphs and charts are as follows:

- Red,
- Yellow,
- Purple,
- Grey.

 DARK BLUE CMYK 100-61-37-18 HEX #104967 RGB 16-73-103			
 GREY CMYK 50-30-25-30 HEX #5D6C78 RGB 94-108-120			

Figure 3: Primary and secondary colors to be used in POSEIDON

2.2 PROJECT TEMPLATES

Project Word and PPT templates for reports and technical presentation, respectively, have been co-developed together with a design agency contracted by partner Steinbeis. The templates are available on the project sharepoint (available via [this link](#)). The templates can be adapted during the project to match future needs.

Figure 4: Project PPT template

Figure 5: Project Word template (first two pages of report)

2.3 FLYER

A project flyer has been designed to promote the POSEIDON project when partners attend meetings and events with external stakeholders. It will be available in different formats: as a folded leaflet to be printed and handed to external stakeholders at conference booths and as digital material available for all for download on the project website. A first batch of flyers will be printed and distributed to project partners (20 flyers per partner) during the consortium meeting in September 2024.

The POSEIDON project four-fold flyer is designed with a cover page featuring POSEIDON's logo and the image of Valencia's port. When the flyer unfolds, two pages appear featuring project related information such as the project's objectives with a picture of the port of Thessaloniki on page 2, and the project's key facts with a picture of the port of Valencia on page 3. Furthermore, when those two pages are unfolded further, the project's value chain is represented in a visually appealing manner alongside project pictures together with the description of the expected outcomes on the right side. The back page of the flyer features logos of all partners, the EU emblem, the links to the social media channels, and a QR code that directs interested parties to the project website.

The project is co-funded with nearly €10 million by the European Commission

2 pilot sites in Valencia and Thessaloniki to demonstrate the value chains based on e-methanol as fuel for shipping

PARTNERS

FOLLOW US!

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement 10107916.

MAIN OBJECTIVES ARE:

1. Build and test an innovative a technology readiness level 7 e-methanol pilot plant
2. Establish two communities of practice in Thessaloniki and Valencia
3. Assess the impacts of the value chain implementation through detailed studies
4. Develop an EU roadmap to best deploy renewable fuel solutions in EU
5. Promote public acceptance of POSEIDON solutions

VALUE CHAIN WITH MAIN INNOVATIONS

Figure 6: POSEIDON four-fold flyer with its two sides

2.4 ROLL-UP

A rollup has been designed and will be printed in June 2024. It presents key facts about the project such as its duration, its main goal, the involved partners and a key visual representing the POSEIDON methodology and main objectives. The rollup will be displayed at every big dissemination event and put in the background of the speaker when the project is presented at online events. A digital version will be available for download on the project sharepoint and website. The roll-up will be unveiled at the next consortium meeting in September 2024.

Figure 7: Several views of the POSEIDON roll-up

2.5 PROJECT PRESENTATION

A presentation of the POSEIDON project for the general public was produced by Steinbeis. Based on the POSEIDON's PPT template, it includes 5 to 10 slides featuring information on the project, its objectives, its main results, a description of the POSEIDON value chain and of the two use cases of Valencia and Thessaloniki. It will presents the consortium as well as contact information and link to the website and social media accounts. This presentation will also be uploaded on the POSEIDON website and made available in the “Resources & Link” section. In March 2024, a first version of the project presentation was created for the COP meeting in Valencia. This version was updated in May 2024 to include the latest versions of the key visuals. Both versions are available on the project website sharepoint ([link](#)).

2.6 PROJECT VIDEO

A promotional video will be developed and produced in collaboration with a professional communication agency specialised in video editing. CDE lead partner Steinbeis will draft the video script based on key messages to be conveyed collected from partners’ feedback. The video will present the objectives of POSEIDON and explain the project technologies and expected benefits via animations, statements and video shots featuring both use cases of Thessaloniki and Valencia. The video production will start during the second year of POSEIDON and the video will be published by M30 on the social media channels and if deemed necessary on a video platform such as YouTube.

2.7 PRESS PACKAGE

Press releases will be published on the project webpage, websites of POSEIDON partners and on platforms dedicated to EU projects to highlight main project activities and achievements. They will be drafted as short press articles and will contain a maximum of one to two pictures. In total, five

press releases will be issued during the project lifetime with a planned last press release to be drafted after project end to announce the closure of the project. The first one was released just after the kick-off meeting in Karlsruhe in September 2023 (see Annex). The second one is planned to be published in late summer/fall 2024.

2.8 PROJECT NEWSLETTER

Project newsletters will be published every year to have four newsletters issued by the end of the project. Each edition will feature a short editorial and three to five articles informing on the progress of the project tasks, the achievements of milestones and key results and the organization and participation of partners in scientific conferences and main EU events. The newsletters will be distributed to all project partners and to interested external partners who subscribed to the POSEIDON newsletter via the webpage (a registration plugin is integrated into the webpage to allow visitors to register). All project partners will be asked by the CDE leader Steinbeis to disseminate the project newsletters to their own network to increase the total outreach. The first project newsletter will be released by the end of M13 in September 2024.

2.9 SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS & STRATEGY

Developing a strategy for social media usage is crucial as most of the actors in the industry, scientific and policy fields as well as the general public use such media. Therefore, social media channels are unique channels to interact with these stakeholders and build an online presence together with the project website. They also allow for a more tangible engagement than a website, by giving the impression of proximity and enabling a two-way communication in real time. The official POSEIDON project LinkedIn and X accounts were created in December 2023. The LinkedIn account will serve as the main news platform and X will be considered as a support media channel.

A social media strategy was developed by partner Steinbeis and presented to the coordinator in January 2024. The plan is to update both social media accounts regularly to build more connections with the main target groups. The frequency of posting will be set at a minimum of one new post every two weeks and the objective is to have around 1,000 followers by the end of the project.

The LinkedIn account can be accessed via following link: [POSEIDON LinkedIn](#).

Figure 8: Screenshot of the POSEIDON LinkedIn account taken in April 2024

The project’s X channel will serve to post short messages on the project and its progress and advertise project events. It can be accessed via following link: [POSEIDON X](#).

Figure 9: Screenshot of the POSEIDON X account taken in April 2024

If deemed necessary, a dedicated YouTube channel will be created to share all project videos including the general project video to be produced within POSEIDON (see subchapter 2.6).

3 PROJECT WEBSITE

As an essential element of the communication strategy, the POSEIDON website will provide information about project advancements, and results achieved. The visitors of the website will also have access to publications, public deliverables, as well as information on activities performed by the project partners (e.g. webinars, events). The website will remain online at least up to two years after the closing of the project.

The website has been developed and will be maintained and updated continuously by Steinbeis, with the contribution from all the POSEIDON partners and the support of a design agency. It aims to fulfil the following specific objectives:

- Provide contact information for external stakeholders,
- Provide a brief project presentation and project information,
- Provide information about the POSEIDON consortium and the role of the partners, and a link to the partner organizations' websites,
- Inform stakeholders about the results or activities of POSEIDON and events around the project,
- Act as an online knowledge repository (public deliverables, publications, communication materials such as flyers, etc.).

The POSEIDON website will be available via the following link “project-poseidon.eu” from the start of June 2024.

3.1 WEBSITE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

The POSEIDON website was designed by Die Komplizen (<https://komplizen.de>), a German design agency, in close collaboration with CDE leader Steinbeis. It is compliant with the POSEIDON project corporate identity described in chapter 2. The website, entirely set up in English, was developed using WordPress (<https://wordpress.com/>).

3.2 WEBSITE STRUCTURE

The information available on the POSEIDON website is currently structured in six main sections, all accessible directly from the website's header row (menu bar, on top). The navigation has been made easy so that a first-time visitor can easily find the information he or she is looking for. The six sections are as follows:

- Homepage,
- About POSEIDON (with two subsections: Background and objectives and Main innovations and expected impact),
- Use cases (with two subsections: Thessaloniki and Valencia),
- Consortium,
- News & events,
- Resources & Links.

In addition, links to social media channels (LinkedIn and X account) can be found on the menu top right side and in the footer of the site as well.

3.3 HOMEPAGE

The “Homepage” is the landing page where the visitor can discover the POSEIDON project, its

identity and what the project intends to do. It features information on main goal and solutions to be developed. At the top of the homepage section is the menu bar with the POSEIDON logo, which, when clicked in any section of the webpage, will redirect the visitor to the Homepage.

Figure 10: Screenshot of the POSEIDON website Homepage

Overall, the homepage is split into different parts as explained below:

- “Key numbers” presenting in a visually appealing way the most relevant key information of the project,
- “Goal of the Horizon Europe project POSEIDON” part placed in a prominent position of the Homepage presenting the project main objective and providing a transfer bouton to the “About POSEIDON” section,
- “Main innovations and project results” part providing an overview of the main innovations to be developed,
- “Latest news” part at the bottom of the page providing a display of POSEIDON’s most recent news from the “News & events”part.

3.4 “ABOUT POSEIDON” SECTION

The “About POSEIDON” section contains the two subsections “Background and objectives” and “Main innovations and expected impacts”, respectively. Those two subsections can also be accessed directly from the menu bar.

The first subsection provides a detailed description of the reasons behind the project (so called background) and the goal of the POSEIDON project which is to mainstream the use of e-methanol as fuel for shipping. It is followed by an overview of the project objectives and a key visual of the POSEIDON project methodology which highlights its triple strategy:

- 1) Technological level: advance the TRL of the ICODOS power-to-e-methanol pilot plant by performing demonstration tests in relevant operational environment and test the produced e-methanol in 2-stroke and 4-stroke engines in laboratory environment and in a pilot boat on open sea in Sweden,
- 2) Case study level: lay the foundations of a value chain implementation in the ports of Valencia and Thessaloniki by forming Communities of practice (COPs), understand needs of key stakeholders and barriers and evaluate different implementation scenarios and assessing their impacts,
- 3) EU level: facilitate knowledge exchange with EU players, reduce barriers to implementation and prepare for deployment and replication at EU level.

Figure 11: Key visual of the technology, case study and EU level developed for the POSEIDON project

This subsection is followed by the second one “Main innovations and expected impacts” starting with the presentation of the project main innovations accompanied by a key visual showcasing the POSEIDON value chain and its three main steps (feedstock, production and end use).

Figure 12: key visual of the POSEIDON project value chain

Furthermore, a description of the project’s expected outcomes is included at the bottom of the page.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

- **Improved renewable fuel technologies:** more cost efficient and performant technologies for e-methanol production, storage, distribution and end-use based on EU research and innovation,
- **Value chain implementation:** two value chains implemented in the ports of Thessaloniki and Valencia based on POSEIDON research outputs,
- **E-methanol becomes a standard marine fuel:** new built maritime ships equipped with 2-stroke and 4-stroke e-methanol engines,
- **Ports as e-methanol hubs:** deployment of an infrastructure for e-methanol production, storage and distribution in the main EU ports,
- **Enabling environment:** favourable regulatory framework and new standards for the use of e-methanol onboard ships and the safe production, transport and distribution of renewable fuels in EU,
- **Social acceptance:** EU citizens are better informed about the benefits of e-methanol as renewable marine fuel thanks to a targeted communication campaign.

Figure 13: Screenshot of the POSEIDON project expected impacts part of the website

3.5 “USE CASES” SECTION

The "Use cases" section provides information on the two pilots of the POSEIDON project and is therefore divided into two sub-pages, "Thessaloniki" and "Valencia". The first item presented in this section is a visual representation of Europe’s largest ports by goods handled. It is followed by the

description of the two project pilots the form of two tables having the same structure to allow easy comparison between the two use cases. The content for this section was co-developed in close collaboration with the pilot sites partners of Spain and Greece to ensure reliability of data.

About Poseidon ▼ [Use cases](#) ▼ Consortium News & events Resources & Links

THESSALONIKI

Port's characteristics

Port	Thessaloniki
Sea basin	Aegean Sea
Port's area	1.5 km ²
Yearly cargo traffic	7.3 million tons (2023)
Direct employment	525

Case study description

Location of plant: The Thessaloniki case study consists of the CAO plant producing lime located in the greater port area, 10 km away from the port. The plant produces approximately 24,000 tons of CO₂ from limestone calcination and a total of 34,000 tons of CO₂ annually.

E-methanol plant characteristics

Feedstock: CO₂ emissions come from the lime manufacturing process at the CAO's plant and are either recovered from the exhaust gas emissions of the heat production unit or from the so-called lime-off gases, a subproduct of CaCO₃ reaction. The technical options regarding water and energy supply for

About Poseidon ▼ [Use cases](#) ▼ Consortium News & events Resources & Links

Valencia

Port's characteristics

Port	Valencia
Sea basin	Mediterranean Sea
Port's area	5.6 km ²
Yearly cargo traffic	79 million tons (2022)
Direct employment	17,973

Case study description

Location of plant: Two wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) operated by partner GOMSL located close to Valenciaport: Pinedo and Quart Benàger. Pinedo generates about 6,000 tons CO₂/year while Quart Benàger about 1,500 tons CO₂/year.

E-methanol plant characteristics

Feedstock: H₂ will be produced locally via an electrolyser supplied by local on-site power generation (solar PV) and additional renewable energy purchased on the market. Hydrogen will be stored and later fed to the ICODOS technology together

Figure 14: Screenshot of the ports' descriptions showed on the POSEIDON webpage

3.6 “CONSORTIUM” SECTION

The „Consortium“ section allows visitors to gain information on the nineteen project partners. The section features an introductory paragraph on the overall composition of the consortium followed by a map with all logos of the partner organizations which, when clicked, provide a short description of the main activities of the partner, its role in the project and a link to the partner website via a pop-up functionality.

Consortium

The POSEIDON consortium consists of a total of 19 partners from 7 countries including 8 industrial partners, 5 research organisations, 2 ports, 2 business support organisations, 1 biomass association and 1 public agency. All partners are fully committed to accelerate the transition towards renewable fuels in EU shipping.

Click on the logos below to find out more about an organisation and its role as a partner in the consortium. Please note that the project partner 'Inventors' and its affiliated partner 'CAO Hellas' are presented as a single partner.

Figure 15: Screenshot of the “Consortium” section (top part)

Figure 16: Screenshot of the partner description available via the pop-up function

3.7 “NEWS & EVENTS” SECTION

A very important section of the POSEIDON website is “News & events” which will be regularly updated with news (on project progress, submitted publications, etc) and information on planned and held events (workshops, conferences, meetings, etc.) relevant for the POSEIDON partners and the main target groups. Four of the project most recent news/events will be displayed on the website Homepage via the “Latest post” part in order to attract the attention of the visitors, and when a user clicks on a news item, he or she will be redirected to the “News & events” page where they can access all the news published.

Thumbnail	Date	Title	Text Snippet
	17/5/2024	POSEIDON features in CORDIS's Synergy Info Pack	We are honored by the inclusion of the POSEIDON project in the latest CORDIS Synergy Info Pack, entitled "Waterborne Transport for a Green Future". This essential
	18/4/2024	POSEIDON's local communities of practice (COP)	One of the objectives of the POSEIDON project is to set up Communities of Practice (COP) in Valencia and Thessaloniki to prepare the implementation of
	8/3/2024	International Women's Day	Today is International Women's Day and we would like to take this opportunity to celebrate our female colleagues involved in the POSEIDON project! As the gender dimension plays...
	7/3/2024	Second partner meeting in Valencia	The members of the EU project POSEIDON gathered in Valencia on March 5 and 6, 2024 for the project's second Consortium meeting. The two-days event took place at...

Figure 17: Screenshot of the News & events section

3.8 “RESOURCES” SECTION

This section features all public deliverables, publications and communication materials (e.g. project logo and newsletter) related to the POSEIDON project developed during the project lifetime. To maximize the impacts of the project, this section will also provide information on similar EU projects and EU partnerships with which POSEIDON collaborates. Meetings and discussions already took place with similar EU projects Butterfly (GA 101118241) and Fuelphoria (GA 101118286).

Figure 18: Screenshot of the related projects represented on the POSEIDON website

3.9 FOOTER

The footer shows the EU funding claim with the corresponding European Union flag as well as the following funding acknowledgement:

“Funded by the European Union Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement No. 101117616. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them. “

Furthermore, the footer of the webpage provides contact information, links to the project’s social media accounts and a subscribe button to register to automatically receive the project newsletters. The footer also contains a link to the imprint section and privacy policy section of the website, ensuring that visitors to the website have all the necessary information concerning the website publishers and the provisions relating to data protection.

Figure 19: Screenshot of the footer of the POSEIDON webpage

4 CONCLUSION

The D7.2 on promotional toolkit and website is the second deliverable of WP7 on communication, dissemination and exploitation. It provides a detailed overview of the key printed and digital communication materials such as the project flyer, roll-up, and website. These materials are crucial for maximizing the impacts of POSEIDON during and after the project.

The communication materials, described in Chapter 2, will guide and support partners in effectively communicating about the project. The POSEIDON website, which is due to be launched at the start of June 2024, will serve as an important communication channel throughout the duration of the project together with the social media channels. Partner Steinbeis will be responsible for updating the communication materials to reflect changes and posting regular news on the project progress on the webpage and social media. To ensure that the information communicated is correct, partners will be asked to validate all content before it is published.

5 ANNEX - FIRST PRESS RELEASE PUBLISHED IN SEPTEMBER 2023

European project POSEIDON: paving the way for the decarbonization of European shipping sector with synthetic methanol

Horizon Europe project POSEIDON has just started: the POSEIDON project officially started on September 1st 2023 and will run for 48 months. It focuses on the production and the use of synthetic methanol (e-methanol) as fuel in shipping. The kick-off meeting was held in Karlsruhe, Germany, on September 6th and 7th bringing together 19 organizations from 7 EU countries. The 2-day event allowed partners to get to know each other, to validate an action plan for the upcoming months for a smooth implementation of the project, and to have a first exchange with the members of the Advisory Board who will provide guidance throughout the project.

POSEIDON as key enabler of new value chains based on synthetic methanol

The overall goal of the POSEIDON project is to demonstrate the use of synthetic methanol for the decarbonization of the shipping sector. The project will prepare the implementation of local value chains based on e-methanol as fuel for shipping in the ports of Valencia, Spain and Thessaloniki, Greece. This will be achieved by connecting local stakeholders and collecting requirements through the formation of locally organized groups of people who collaborate regularly (so called Communities of Practice) and by building a performant power-to-e-methanol demonstration plant based on a novel concept including CO₂ capture and production of e-methanol. This plant will be tested in relevant operational environments and the produced e-methanol will be used in 2-stroke and 4-stroke engines to evaluate the fuel quality and compatibility.

Detailed technical, economic, environmental, and social assessments will be performed to quantify the economic value created under different scenarios and to identify potential barriers and optimisation potentials. To pave the way for market uptake and future deployment of e-methanol in the EU, local roadmaps and a replication tool to evaluate the feasibility of deployment of e-methanol in EU ports will be developed, so that external EU stakeholders can make use of the results of POSEIDON.

An important aspect of the project will be to foster public acceptance by raising awareness of the benefits of new renewable fuels for shipping, in particular methanol. Project partners plan to regularly share project activities, progress and achievements with academia, industry, policy makers and other relevant stakeholders.

First partner meeting in Karlsruhe to kick-start the first activities

The inaugural meeting of POSEIDON was organized over two days. On the first day, the project

coordinator and work package leaders presented the main activities of the project.

In the afternoon, partner Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) invited all partners to a visit of the Energy lab 2.0 located at the KIT campus North. Energy Lab 2.0 is a cooperative project of the three Helmholtz Centres KIT, Forschungszentrum Jülich and German Aerospace Center. It is a test bed where several innovative energy solutions including Power-to-X plants, storage solutions and hydrogen electrolyzers are demonstrated. It allows to run real simulations and test cutting-edge sector coupling technologies for shaping the future German energy system. Project partners could have a look at the proof-of-concept e-methanol plant to be upscaled within POSEIDON. After the site visit, partners enjoyed a short city tour in Karlsruhe and a joint dinner.

The second day was dedicated to first meetings between the consortium and the EC project officer as well as the members of the Advisory Board. These were followed by short workshops moderated by work package leaders that helped in kick-starting early project tasks and assigning responsibilities to ensure a smooth implementation of POSEIDON. The next partner meeting will take place in March 2024.

Group picture of POSEIDON project partners during kickoff meeting

POSEIDON as a driver of fossil fuels removal and decarbonization of EU shipping industry

POSEIDON will help decrease the dependence on fossil fuels which will make the EU less subject to economic and political pressures in line with the REPowerEU plan. The project will contribute to mainstream synthetic methanol as fuel in EU ports and the associated key technologies such as e-methanol production plants and engines for ships. Several players positioned all along the value chain such as industrial feedstock providers, engineering companies specialised in renewable synthetic fuels, ports, project developers, engine manufacturers and ship builders are expected to benefit from the growing e-methanol market. Furthermore, the steady implementation of e-methanol based value chains across EU will contribute to the decarbonization of EU ports and shipping. The new methods, tools and results produced by POSEIDON will be shared with the scientific and research community and EU citizens to respectively promote innovation and raise awareness of benefits of synthetic fuels for clean shipping.

The POSEIDON project in short

The project, coordinated by European Institute for Energy Research (EIFER), started in September 2023 and will run until August 2027. It consists of 19 partners from 7 European countries: EIFER, EDF, KIT, RINA, Fundación Valenciaport, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, ICODOS, Fincantieri, Isotta Fraschini Motori - IFM, Winterthur Gas & Diesel - WinGD, Steinbeis Innovation gGmbH, Global Omnium, Port of Thessaloniki – ThPA S.A., CERTH, CNR-STEMS, Swedish Maritime Administration, Inventors, CAO Hellas, and AVEBIOM.

POSEIDON is receiving funding from the European Union’s research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101117616. The European Commission is co-funding the project with nearly € 9,7 million. Activities of Swiss project partner WinGD are co-funded by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

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